

EXOTIC MUONIC-HYDROGEN IN III-IV NITRIDE ARTIFICIAL ATOMS

Faithful Ajah

A report presented to fulfill the criteria for a Bachelor's
degree at the Department of Physics

Michael Okpara University

Abia, Nigeria

DECEMBER 2022

Supervisor: Dr. C.I Oriaku

Abstract

The findings from this study have brought to light a better perspective for the understanding of muons in interaction with a cavity. Nitride materials have ushered in scientific and technological breakthroughs for lighting, mass data storage, and high-power electronic applications. Despite the current development, there are still technological problems that impede the performance of such devices. Quantum confinement of muons in the nitride cavity is used in this work, and the results are compared to that of the electron confinement. The properties are theoretically studied using the particle in a box approximation and the lifetimes estimated by the Gamow lifetime approximation. The results show that the ground state confinement energy largely depends on the cavity's confining length. Thus, as the confining length decreases, the confinement energy increases. The energies from the muonic atoms were also found to be significantly higher than that of the electronic hydrogen. Hence, higher confinement energies can be obtained and tuned by decreasing the confining length of the confined muonic hydrogen in the nitride cavity. Also, the theoretically calculated lifetime increased with increasing confining length, with the muonic atoms displaying much less lifetime than their electronic counterparts. Hence the muonic atoms of higher energy will be short-lived compared to the electronic atoms.

DECLARATION

I confirm that this project is the original work approved and supervised by the supervisory committee and carried out by Ajah Faithful Miracle with the registration number MOUAU/PHY/17/100573 in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Science Degree (B.Sc) in the Department of Physics.

Signature.....

Date.....

Ajah Faithful Miracle

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My gratitude goes to God Almighty for the success of this research and to all who in one way or the other contributed immensely to the successful completion of this research.

Special thanks to my supervisor Dr. Chijioke Oriaku for his supervision at every stage of this work. His advice will never be forgotten. I also wish to thank all my lecturers in the Department.

I am grateful to my parents and siblings for their encouragement and support towards the successful completion of this work.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Cover page	i
Declaration	ii
Certification	iii
Dedication	iv
Acknowledgement	v
Table of content	vi
List of Tables	viii
List of Figures	ix
Abstract	x

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of study	1
1.2 Statement of problem	2
1.3 Aim of study	3

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Particle in a box model	4
2.2 Radioactive decay	6
2.2.1 Gamow theory of alpha decay	7

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction	10
3.2 Numerical calculation	10
3.2.1 Effective mass	10
3.2.2 Reduced mass	10
3.2.3 Gamow lifetime approximation	11
3.2.4 Schrödinger radial equation	12

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result	15
4.2 Discussion	18

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion	21
5.2 Recommendation	21
References	

LIST OF TABLES

3.1: Electron and hole effective masses	11
3.2 Dielectric constant of the materials	11
4.1: Calculated reduced masses for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs	14
4.2: Calculated binding energies for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs.	14
4.3: Calculated Bohr for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs	15

LIST OF FIGURES

2.1: Particle in a box	4
4.1: The confinement energy of the InN cavity.	17
4.2: The confinement energy of the GaN cavity	17
4.3: The confinement energy of the BN cavity	17
4.4: The confinement energy of the AlN cavity	17
4.5: The Lifetime of the InN cavity	18
4.5: The Lifetime of the GaN cavity	19
4.5: The Lifetime of the BN cavity	19
4.5: The Lifetime of the AlN cavity	20

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Artificial atoms refer to a whole class of systems that behave like atoms in the sense of discrete energy levels, not just quantum dots. Modern semiconductor technology makes it possible to fabricate particles of metal or "pools" of electrons in a semiconductor that are only a few hundred angstroms in size. Electrons in these structures can display astounding behavior. Such structures, coupled to electrical leads through tunnel junctions, have been given various names: single-electron transistors, quantum dots, zero-dimensional electron gases, and Coulomb islands. Essentially, artificial atoms are atoms whose effective nuclear charge is controlled by metallic electrodes. Like natural atoms, these small electronic systems contain a discrete number of electrons and have a discrete spectrum of energy levels. Artificial atoms, however, have a unique and spectacular property: The current through such an atom or the capacitance between its leads can vary by many orders of magnitude when its charge is changed by a single electron (Hüfner et al., 1977).

These artificial atoms are man-made nanostructures that emulate the behavior of real atoms but give scientists the flexibility to design them for specific purposes. In these atoms, discrete energy levels are manufactured to get specific desired results.

Muons are like electrons, but only heavier. Muons are therefore also elementary particles, like electrons. But muons only live for 2.2 microseconds and they are 200 times heavier than electrons. Muonic hydrogen is an exotic hydrogen atom, where a muon (instead of an electron) orbits the proton (Fleming et al., 2011). Because the muon is 200 times heavier than the electron, the muon's orbit is 200 times closer to the proton in muonic hydrogen than that of the electron in regular hydrogen. This 200 times smaller orbit means that the muon "feels" the size of the proton (Paul Scherrer Institute, 1990).

In this work, the Quantum confinement of the muonic hydrogen-like atom in a semiconductor artificial atom is theoretically investigated. The Gamow theory of alpha decay is modified to calculate the lifetime of the muon in the artificial atom from the obtained binding energy of the muonic hydrogen-like confined in a medium.

1.2 . Statement of Problem

The fusion of atomic nuclei with muons have been found to be more likely to be achieved than that of electrons (Jones 1986). This is due to the fact that their orbits are much closer to the nucleus than the electrons, but a problem arises from the fact that muons are unstable- they have a short lifespan of about $2.2\mu\text{s}$ after which they decay into an electron and some neutrinos. Reliable muon sources can be made with a high-energy particle accelerator which takes about -5Gev to produce. After fusing the helium muonic nuclei, the total energy produced would be about $+2.7\text{Gev}$ (when

the muon fuses it aids the fusion of other muons but at some point gets stuck, this is what causes a stop in the generation of energy). If the muons are more stable, it reduces the probability of encountering the alpha sticking problem (Jackson, 1957).

In order to provide a solution to the unstable nature of the muon and consequently the alpha sticking problem, the lifetime of the muon in various artificial atoms is investigated. Theoretically, we confine the muon in an artificial atom and investigate the lifetime using a modified gamow-like model.

1.3 Significance of Study

The findings from this study will bring to light a better perspective for the understanding of muon in interaction with a cavity. A search for a more stable muon is one of the quests in nuclear engineering. Confining muons in a cavity may in turn increase their life from the current $2.2\mu\text{s}$ in air to a higher lifetime in a cavity. This may lead to stabilizing muons for a more successful fusion of atomic nuclei and thus help with a more economical approach to utilizing them.

1.4 Aim of the Study

- To review and modify the theory of binding energy of muonic hydrogen-like atoms in a confined medium.
- To calculate and derive an expression for the lifetimes of muonic hydrogen from the Gamow theory of alpha decay.

- To calculate numerically, the lifetimes of muonic hydrogen at different confining lengths.
- To calculate the confinement energy of muonic hydrogen in various nitride cavities.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Particle in a box model.

In quantum mechanics, the particle in a box model (also known as the infinite potential well or the infinite square well) describes a particle free to move in a small space surrounded by impenetrable barriers. The model is mainly used as a hypothetical example to illustrate the differences between classical and quantum systems. In classical systems, for example, a particle trapped inside a large box can move at any speed within the box and it is no more likely to be found at one position than another. However, when the well becomes very narrow (on the scale of a few nanometers), quantum effects become important. The particle may only occupy certain positive energy levels. Likewise, it can never have zero energy, meaning that the particle can never "sit still". Additionally, it is more likely to be found at certain positions than at others, depending on its energy level. The particle may never be detected at certain positions, known as spatial nodes.

The simplicity of this model makes it possible to gain insight into quantum effects without the necessity of complex mathematics. It provides a simple illustration of how quantizations of energy (energy levels), occur in more complicated quantum systems like atoms and molecules.

Fig. 2.1 particle in a box (Vorobiev, 2010)

The simplest form of the particle in a box model is considered a one-dimensional system. Here, the particle may only move backward and forwards along a straight line with impenetrable barriers at either end (Davies et al, n.d). The walls of a one-dimensional box may be seen as regions of space with infinitely large potential energy, space $V(x) = \infty$, while inside the box has a constant zero energy potential $V(x) = 0$, the one-dimensional box can be visualized. The potential energy in this model is given as:

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 < x < L \\ \infty, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

where L is the length of the box, and x is the position of the particle within the box. The wave function $\psi(x, t)$ and energy levels of a particle inside the box can be obtained by solving the Schrodinger equation (Lodovilo, 2015):

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(x,t)}{\partial t} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \psi(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + V(x)\psi(x, t) \quad (2.2)$$

The dispersion relation of the particle is given by the expression:

$$E = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_r} \quad (2.3)$$

Thus energies corresponding to each of the allowed wave numbers is given as:

$$E_n = \frac{n^2 h^2}{8m_r L^2} \quad (2.4)$$

Where the reduced effective mass

$$m_r = \frac{m_\mu m_{nuc}}{m_\mu + m_{nuc}} \quad (2.5)$$

m_{nuc} is the mass of the nucleus which represents the hole, and m_μ is the mass of the muon.

Eqn. (2.3) is called the particle in a box model. Where L is the length of the box, m is the mass of the particle, and n is the quantum number, which implies the lowest amount of energy of the particle is never zero.

In Quantum Dots, the confinement of a muon and hole within the dot is just the same as a particle in a box. Thus, allowing particle in a box approximation to be applied.

However, considering the little discrepancies arising from the different number of particles and shapes which include (1) one particle and a squared shape for the particle in a box. (2) Two particles (Muon and Hole) and a spherical shape for QDs. Hence, the following adjustments were made: Firstly, the length of the box L is interchanged with radius R for QDs. Secondly, the masses of Muon and hole (which will be replaced by the mass of the nucleus) are replaced by their effective masses due to their interaction with the crystal lattice. Thus, the confinement energy of the muons in QDs becomes:

$$E = \frac{n h^2}{8m_\mu R^2} + \frac{n h^2}{8m_{nuc} R^2}, n = 1 \quad (2.6)$$

The ground state confinement energy of the electron in QDs becomes:

$$E = \frac{h^2}{8R^2} \left(\frac{1}{m_\mu} + \frac{1}{m_{nuc}} \right) \quad (2.7)$$

2.2 Radioactive decay

Radioactive decay (also known as nuclear decay, radioactivity, radioactive disintegration, or nuclear disintegration) is the process by which an unstable atomic nucleus loses energy by radiation. A material containing unstable nuclei is considered radioactive. Three of the most common types of decay are alpha decay (α -decay), beta decay (β -decay), and gamma decay (γ -decay), all of which involve emitting one or more particles. The weak force is the mechanism that is responsible for beta decay, while the other two are governed by the electromagnetic and strong forces. The decaying nucleus is called the parent radionuclide (or parent radioisotope), and the process produces at least one daughter nuclide. Except for gamma decay or internal conversion from a nuclear-excited state, the decay is a nuclear transmutation resulting in a daughter containing a different number of protons or neutrons (or both). When the number of protons changes, an atom of a different chemical element is created.

- Alpha decay occurs when the nucleus ejects an alpha particle (helium nucleus).
- Beta decay occurs in two ways;
 - (i) Beta-minus decay, is when the nucleus emits an electron and an antineutrino in a process that changes a neutron to a proton.

(ii) Beta-plus decay, is when the nucleus emits a positron and a neutrino in a process that changes a proton to a neutron, also known as positron emission.

- In gamma decay a radioactive nucleus first decays by the emission of an alpha or beta particle. The daughter nucleus that results is usually left in an excited state and it can decay to a lower energy state by emitting a gamma ray photon.

2.2.1 Gamow theory of alpha decay.

In 1928, George Gamow used some knowledge about tunneling and the WKB approximation (to the one-dimensional time-independent Schrodinger equation) to provide the first theoretical account of alpha decay (emission of 2 protons and 2 neutrons, by heavy nuclei). Alpha emission is possible only when $Q > 0$, (where Q is the difference in the binding energy between the parent nuclei and the daughter nucleus). This is an essential condition, but not a sufficient condition. Gamow's theory is based on Quantum Mechanical tunneling or barrier penetration. Gamow's theory was the first verification of the quantum mechanical tunneling process. Classically, a particle cannot cross the barrier i.e., its energy is smaller than the barrier height but quantum mechanically the particle can penetrate (or) tunnel through the barrier. The energy of the particle inside the potential well increases by an amount ΔE which overshoots the barrier height in a short time Δt , which is given by Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. Due to the uncertainty limit, this energy increase is undetectable. For given energy E , a particle with a smaller mass has a larger velocity, and

can cross the barrier easily in a small-time t . Thus, the spontaneous emission of lighter particles like α particle is more probable than heavier particles. The alpha particles within the nucleus must present themselves again and again at the barrier surface until conditions are ripe for penetration. Alpha particles are in constant motion and bounce back and forth from the barrier walls. In each collision with the wall, there is a definite probability that it will decay through the barrier. Let n be the frequency with which the alpha particle collides to escape the nucleus, and P be the probability of transmission in each collision. The relation between half-life ($T_{1/2}$) and decay constant (λ) is given by:

$$T_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{\lambda} \quad (2.8)$$

where λ is the probability of decay per second.

$$\lambda = \frac{P}{T} \quad (2.9)$$

where T is the time interval between two successive collisions of the alpha particle and barrier wall. Thus;

$$T = \frac{2r_0}{V_a} \quad (2.10)$$

Here, V_a is the velocity of the alpha particle.

$$n = \frac{V_a}{2r_0} \quad (2.11)$$

where n is the frequency of the particle.

$$\lambda = nP \quad (2.12)$$

$$P = \frac{|\psi_2|}{|\psi_1|} \quad (2.13)$$

where ψ_2 is the wave function outside the barrier and ψ_1 is the wave function inside the barrier. To obtain the probability we consider the Schrodinger equation,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2\mu}{\hbar} [(Q - V)] \psi = 0 \quad (2.14)$$

Where μ is the reduced mass

It turns out that if the alpha particle wants to escape out of the nucleus, for which it should have a maximum energy as represented by the curve. Similarly, if an alpha particle wants to penetrate the nucleus from outside, we know that it should have energy at least equal to or greater than that of the potential barrier. Thus, in both ways, the particle will have to cross the barrier of the given height 'E'. The solution of the Schrodinger equation is,

$$\Psi = Ae^{\frac{is}{\hbar}} \quad (2.15)$$

Substituting the solution in the equation and simplifying we get,

$$\left(\frac{ds}{dr}\right) = \pm \sqrt{2\mu(Q - V)} \quad (2.16)$$

In the tunneling region,

$$\int_{r=r_0}^{r=r_2} ds = \int_{r_0}^{r_2} i\rho dr \quad (2.17)$$

$$\text{Where } \rho = \sqrt{2\mu(V - Q)} \quad (2.18)$$

Using the above relation and the wave function at $r = r_0$ and at $r = r_2$, we get,

$$P = e^{-2 \int_{r_0}^{r_2} \frac{1}{\hbar} (\sqrt{2\mu(V-Q)}) dr} \quad (2.19)$$

Using the equation (2.4) and taking natural logarithm on both sides, we get

$$\ln \lambda = \ln \ln n - 2 \left[\frac{4\pi^2 Z e^2}{h v_a} - \frac{8\pi e}{h} \sqrt{r_0 \mu Z} \right] \quad (2.20)$$

Equation (2.18) gives the final expression for Gamow's theory.

We substitute for the constant values in equation (2.20) to simplify the evaluation for decay constants, and the following equation becomes;

$$\ln \lambda = \ln \ln n + 1.71 \sqrt{\frac{Z}{Q}} - 1.28 \sqrt{ZR} \quad (2.21)$$

Equation (2.21) is used in the computation of the alpha decay half-life.

CHAPTER THREE

Methodology

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, formulae used to investigate the exotic Muonic-Hydrogen in an artificial atom are derived within the framework of the particle in a box and the Gamow model of alpha decay. The theoretical model and numerical approach that allow one to accurately calculate the lifetime of the confined muon is presented here. We consider the artificial atom to be spherically shaped and confined in three dimensions. Using the Schrödinger and Gamow decay equations described in Chapter 2, we present basic equations used to calculate the lifetime of the confined muon.

3.2 Numerical calculation

3.2.1 Effective mass

The effective mass of a particle is the mass that it seems to have when responding to forces, or the mass that it seems to have when interacting with other identical particles in a thermal distribution.

3.2.2 Reduced mass

The distance between the nucleus and the muon of a hydrogen atom in the ground state is a physical constant L given by;

$$L = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon_r\hbar^2}{m_r e^2} \quad (3.1)$$

Where m_r is the exciton reduced mass defined in (2.5) as;

$$m_{r,\mu} = \frac{m_{\mu} m_{nuc}}{m_{\mu} + m_{nuc}}, \quad (3.2)$$

Table 3.1: Electron and hole effective masses (in units of m_0) of the materials (Hanada T., 2013)

Material	m_e	m_h
GaN	0.15	1.3
BN	0.74	0.90
AlN	0.25	1.02
InN	0.12	1.63

3.2.3 Dielectric constant

Table 3.2 Dielectric constant of the materials (Hanada T., 2013)

Material	ϵ_0
GaN	9.7
BN	7.1
AlN	9.4
InN	15.3

3.2.4 Gamow lifetime approximation

After approximations are done to (2.21), an expression for the lifetime of the particle becomes.

$$\tau = \frac{m_{r,\mu} L}{\hbar k} e^{-2\alpha d L} \quad (3.3)$$

Where d is the thickness of the barrier, ' L ' is the distance of the muon from the nucleus.

$$k = \frac{1}{\hbar} \sqrt{2m_{r,\mu} E} \quad (3.4)$$

And,

$$\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{2m_{r,\mu}(V_0 - E)}}{\hbar} \quad (3.5)$$

As the barrier thickness ' d ' reduces such that $d \ll 0$, the equation becomes;

$$\tau = \frac{m_{r,\mu} L}{\hbar k} \quad (3.6)$$

Substituting (3.4) and (3.5) in (3.6), we obtain a simple expression for a muon lifetime in the medium as;

$$\tau_{\mu} = \frac{m_{r,\mu} L}{\sqrt{2m_{r,\mu} E_n}} \quad (3.7)$$

3.2.5 Schrödinger radial equation

The particle-in-a-box model describes the free movement of a particle in a small space surrounded by impenetrable barriers. The ground state energy of a particle trapped in a spherically symmetric box with $V(r) = \infty$ outside and a constant zero potential energy $V(r) = 0$ inside is found by solving the radial part of the Schrodinger equation (Samrat, 2014). The radial part of the Schrödinger equation for the proposed muonic hydrogen-like atom is given as:

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dx_l(r)}{dr} \right) + \left(\frac{2m_{r,\mu} E_\mu}{\hbar^2} - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \right) x_l(r) = E x_l(r) \quad (3.8)$$

Where:

$$m_{r,\mu} = \frac{m_\mu m_{nuc}}{m_\mu + m_{nuc}}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$E_{n,\mu} = \frac{(nh)^2}{8m_\mu R_{cm}^2} + \frac{(nh)^2}{8m_{nuc} R_{cm}^2}, \quad (3.10)$$

Here, R_{cm} represents the center of mass between the muon and nucleus (Rojas et al, 2021).

(3.10) can also be written as.

$$E_{n,\mu} = \frac{(nh)^2}{8R_{cm}^2} \left(\frac{1}{m_\mu} + \frac{1}{m_{nuc}} \right), \quad (3.11)$$

Using (3.9) in (3.11), we have that,

$$E_{n,\mu} = \frac{n^2 \pi^2 \hbar^2}{2m_{r,\mu} R_{cm}^2} \quad (3.12)$$

If we introduce the Bohr radius a_n^2 to the equation, we have that;

$$E_{n,\mu} = \frac{n^2 \pi^2 \hbar^2}{2m_{r,\mu} a_{n,\mu}^2} \left(\frac{a_{n,\mu}^2}{R_{cm}^2} \right) \quad (3.13)$$

So far, nothing has changed because the Bohr radius ratio cancels out.

At ground state ($n=0$), $a_0 \approx R_{cm}$, and:

$$E_{0,\mu} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_{r,\mu} a_0^2} \cdot \left(\frac{a_0^2}{R_{cm}^2} \right) \quad (3.14)$$

Where,

$$a_0 = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2}{m_{r,\mu} e^2} \quad (3.15)$$

Hence, (3.15) becomes;

$$E_{0,\mu} = E_0 \cdot \left(\frac{a_0^2}{R_{cm}^2} \right) \quad (3.16)$$

$$E_{0,\mu} = E_0 \cdot \bar{R}^{-2} \quad (3.17)$$

In equation (3.16), the coefficient E_0 represents the ground state 3D Rydberg energy of the confining cavity and a_0 is the Bohr radius.

Thus, the lifetime of a muonic-hydrogen trapped in the confining cavity can be estimated using;

$$\tau_\mu = \frac{a_0 m_{r,\mu}}{\sqrt{2m_{r,\mu} E_{0\mu}}} \left(\frac{a_0}{R_{cm}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.18)$$

$$\tau_\mu = \frac{a_0 m_{r,\mu}}{\sqrt{2m_{r,\mu} E_{0\mu}}} \bar{R}^{-1} \quad (3.29)$$

Where $m_{r,\mu}$ and $E_{0\mu}$ respectively are the reduced mass and the ground state energy of the muonic hydrogen.

In this work, the set of data in tables 3.1, 3.2, and equations 3.1 to 3.19 was adopted to simulate and determine the physical parameters of GaN, InN, BN, and AlN QDs.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have used the reduced effective mass and Bohr radius approximation to calculate the energies of GaN, BN, AlN, and InN quantum dots as a function of confining length and varying particles. The lifetimes of the muon and electron confined in the various QD materials are also calculated and compared. The results are as reported in this chapter.

Table 4.1: Calculated reduced masses in units of m_0 for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs.

Material	$m_e (m_0)$	$m_\mu (m_0)$
GaN	0.13	27.81
BN	0.21	48.15
AlN	0.20	41.52
InN	0.11	22.22

Table 4.2: Calculated binding energies E_0 (meV) for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs.

Material	E_0 (meV)	$E_{0,\mu}$ (meV)
----------	-------------	-------------------

InN	6.5	1291.5
GaN	19.4	4016.4
BN	54.4	12994.2
AlN	30.9	7128.1

Table 4.3: Calculated Bohr radii a_0 (nm) for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs.

Material	a_0 (nm)	$a_{0,\mu}$ (nm)
InN	7.24	0.04
GaN	3.82	0.02
BN	1.86	0.007
AlN	2.48	0.01

4.1 Confinement Energy of GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs

The confinement energy of GaN, BN, AlN, and InN QDs is determined using the Schrödinger approximation defined in chapters 2 and 3.

The reduced masses of confined electron and muon respectively are used to determine and compare the variations in their confinement energies with respect to the confining cavity.

The plot of confinement energy against confining length \bar{R} for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN semiconductor quantum dots in Fig. 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4 respectively show the dependence of confinement energy on confining length. The results show that ground-state confinement energy is inversely

proportional to confining length. The confinement energy is observed in quantum dots through an increase in the energy of the bandgap. Confinement begins when the radius of the quantum dot material is comparable to or less than the exciton Bohr radius.

As observed in Fig 4.27 confinement began for the electronic hydrogen at a confinement radius of 7.2nm confining the energy of the dot to 0.3eV. The confinement energy increased to 1.3eV in the muonic hydrogen as the confining length reduced to 1nm.

Fig 4.1: The confinement energy of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the InN cavity.

Fig 4.2: The confinement energy of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the GaN cavity.

Fig 4.3: The confinement energy of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the BN cavity.

Fig 4.4: The confinement energy of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the AlN cavity.

4.2 Particle lifetime

The investigation of the lifetime of the muon and electron in the GaN, BN, AlN, and InN quantum dots is based on the fact that the confining length of these particles affects their lifetime. The lifetime is calculated using Eqn. (3.29).

The confining length-dependent change in the lifetime is plotted in Fig. 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, 4.8 for GaN, BN, AlN, and InN quantum dots.

The plot of lifetime against confining length for the various cavities shows the dependence of lifetime on the confining length. In Fig. 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, and 4.8 it is observed that an increase in the confining length causes an increase in the lifetime of the electron and muon.

Fig 4.5: The lifetime of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the InN cavity.

Fig 4.6: The lifetime of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the GaN cavity.

Fig 4.7: The lifetime of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the BN cavity.

Fig 4.8: The lifetime of electronic and muonic hydrogen as a function of the confining length of the AlN cavity.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have investigated theoretically, exotic muonic hydrogen confined in GaN, BN, AlN, and InN quantum dots. The effect of the confinement on the reduced mass, exciton binding energy, lifetime, and ground state confinement energy. The lifetime was studied using a modification to the Gamow lifetime approximation. We presented the physics relating the muonic mass to the energy of the muonic atom and its lifetime when confined in a cavity. We also explained the relationship between the confining length of the particles and their confinement energy.

We also showed how different semiconductor quantum dot materials can change the outcome of the confinement energy and the particle lifetime. It is observed that the decrease in the confining lengths caused an increase in the energy. Also, the theoretically calculated lifetime increased with increasing confining length, with the muonic atoms displaying much less lifetime than their electronic counterparts. Hence the muonic atoms of higher energy will be short-lived compared to the electronic atoms.

5.2 Recommendation

To further validate the accuracy of the result in this work, experimental investigation should be conducted on these theoretically studied muonic hydrogen quantum dots.

REFERENCES

- Anderhub et al (1977)., Phys. Lett. B 71,
443.ADS CrossRef [https://doi.org/10.1016/0370-2693\(77\)90263-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0370-2693(77)90263-5)
- Banin et al (1999). Uri; Cao, YunWei; Katz, David; Millo, Oded (August 1999). "Identification of atomic-like electronic states in indium arsenide nanocrystal quantum dots"
- Bergmann et al (1997). Clemens Schaefer, and Wilhelm Raith, Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 1997, ISBN 3-11-013990-1.
- BYJU'S: radioactivity and alpha decay,
(<https://byjus.com/physics/alpha-decay/>)
- Casperson et al (1977)., Phys. Rev. Lett. 38, 956 ; Phys. Rev. Lett. 38, 1504 (1977).[ADS CrossRef Google Scholar](#)
- Carboni, et al (1977)., Nucl. Phys. A 278, 381; Nuovo Cimento A 34, 493 (1976).[ADS CrossRef Google Scholar](#)
- Cui et al (2019 "Colloidal quantum dot molecules manifesting quantum coupling at room temperature". *Nature Communications*.
- Egan, et al (1980)., Bull. Am. Phys. Soc, 25, 19 .Google Scholar.
- Fleming et al (2011). "Kinetic Isotope Effects for the Reactions of Muonic Helium and Muonium with H₂". *Science*. 331 (6016): 448–450. doi:10.1126/science.1199421. PMID 21273484. S2CID 206530683.
- Hanada, T. (2013). Basic Properties Of GaN, and Related Materials journal of applied physics. P.1-19.
- Hüfner et al (1977) Muonic Atoms, in: "Muon Physics, Vol. 1," V.W. Hughes and CS. Wu, ed., Academic, New York (1977) p. 201. Google Scholar
- Jackson (1957). "Catalysis of Nuclear Reactions between hydrogen isotopes by μ^- Mesons". *Physical Review*. **106** (2): 330.
- Jones (1986). "Muon-Catalysed Fusion Revisited". *Nature*. **321** (6066): 127–133. Bibcode:1986Natur.321..127J. doi:10.1038/321127a0. S2CID 39819102.
- Leisi (1980). μ -Mesic X-rays, in: "High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure," D.F. Measday and A.W. Thomas, ed., North-Holland, Amsterdam p. 3. Google Scholar
- McGraw (2007). Exotic atoms Archived 2007-12-22 at the Wayback Machine, AccessScience, McGraw-Hill. accessdate=September 26, 2007.

Oriaku et al (2021). Confinement Effects and Emission Spectra of α - **GaxIn1-xN** Quantum Dots Nanostructure. Communication in Physical Sciences, 2021, 7(3): 164-173

Paul schiller institute. <https://www.psi.ch/en/muonic-atoms/introduction>

<https://physicsopenlab.org/2015/11/20/quantum-dots-a-true-particle-in-a-box-system/>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box#cite_ref-2

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Effective_mass_\(solid-state_physics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Effective_mass_(solid-state_physics))

P.O. Egan, et al., to be published; Bull. Am. Phys. Soc. 23, 577 (1978).Google Scholar

Ramírez et al (2010). "Optical fine structures of highly quantized InGaAs/GaAs self-assembled quantum dots". *Phys. Rev. B.* **81** (3): 245324.

Rojas R. A. et al. (2021) Confined muonic hydrogen-like atoms, Eur. Phys. J.D 75:116 <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjd/s10053-021-00122-7>.

The University of British Columbia (2021) "The Muonic Helium Atom". Department of Chemistry. News & Events. The chemical interactions of ${}^4\text{H}$ and ${}^4\text{He-}\mu$ are then virtually identical.